

TYPES AND TREATMENT OF ORAL MUCOSAL DISEASE IN CHILDREN

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Abstract: Conditional diseases of the oral mucosa can be divided into 3 groups:

1.traumatist, mechanic, physicist, chemist, stomatitis, leukoplakies (dysplastic, hyperplasty), nicotine stomatitis.

2.medical disease often,but not all experts agree on the disease. This guru was one of the first to turn to Krishna. specialists (oncologists, dermatologists, allergists, an appeal to hematologists sketches.

Key words:herpetic stomatitis, vitaminotherapy, mucosal, leukoplakies, toothpastes, bacteria

Factors that increase the risk of stomatitis origin

- Failure to follow hygiene when eating food fruit eating vegetables, without washing hands, not brushing teeth regularly;
- When using toothpastes that contain a lot of the substance sodium sulfate in constant tooth brushing. This substance reduces the secretion of saliva, and the mucous membrane becomes dry, prone to damage;
- Salivary detachment is reduced even when taking diuretic drugs;
- When artificial teeth are placed – whether they are made of poor-quality material or incorrectly selected sizes;
- Drinking alcohol and smoking tobacco products these substances cause ulcers on the oral mucosa, where favorable conditions for the growth of bacteria arise

Herpetic stomatitis

It is this type of stomatitis that is more common in older people and children. This is due to the fact that about 90% of the population carries the herpes virus in their body, the herpes virus does not call the disease under normal conditions. However, if favorable conditions arise for him – herpes causes stomatitis, for example, in the period of exacerbation of cold hardening, chronic infection — inflammatory diseases, in stressful situations and in the like.in herpetic stomatitis, the body temperature does not rise and signs of general intoxication are not observed, it is simply accompanied by the appearance of many blisters on the mucous membrane of the oral cavity in a short period of time, their natural rupture and the formation of very painful ulcers.

Treatment of herpetic stomatitis

The treatment of herpetic stomatitis includes the following measures:

- Anesthetic preparat Lidocaine, Lido chlorine and so on;
- Locally applied anti-inflammatory agents-Solkoseril, na'matak oil, Cholisal, Kamistad;
- Antiviral drugs-Acyclovir, Zovirax, Bonafton, Alpizarin, Lysotsim, etc.
- Immune-strengthening drugs-Immunal, Cycloferon

Aphthous stomatitis

This type of oral mucosal inflammatory disease always appears chronic. In its clinical form, the head of the mouth manifests itself in the form of numerous wounds, blisters and a whitish rash with red edges. Aphthous stomatitis occurs for months and years, and goes disappears.

Aphthous stomatitis treatment

Aphthous stomatitis treatment: processed (rinsed) with a solution of aphthous boric acid and chamomile. To do this, 1 teaspoon of chamomile powder and 4 gr of boric acid is applied to 300 ml of water and mixed and rinsed the mouth;

It is recommended to dissolve the furacilin tablet in water and rinse the mouth regularly with an antiseptic;

Wipe the affected areas of the oral mucosa with oblipixa oil soaked in cotton;

For the purpose of detoxification-intravenous injection of a solution of sodium sulfate;

The patient is prescribed vitaminotherapy, that is, taking multivitamin complexes.

If aphthous stomatitis does not disappear within 2 weeks, it can also go into the form of severe manifestations – necrotic ulcers. The clinical picture and course of this degree of the disease differ from others, indicating immunodeficiency of the body or poisoning with heavy metal salts.

Candidiasis stomatitis

Stomatitis in this form is caused only by deficits by the immune system. The fact is that all humans will be fungi of the Candida group, which will be in the oral microflora, which, when favorable conditions for reproduction are formed, cause stomata by damaging the oral mucosa. For example, such as diabetes mellitus, immune deficit conditions, long-term treatment with hormonal drugs.

In the specific clinical picture of candidiasis stomatitis: in addition to wounds in the mouth, White caraches are also formed that are difficult to move. This Karash can be easily moved by hand, but a reddened, swollen foci of inflammation remain at the site of the migration, and it is also a favorable place for bacterial growth. Patients complain of severe pain, irritations that arise even when drinking water. In addition, pain is also observed in the corner of the mouth and on the lips.

Treatment of candidiasis stomatitis

Anti-fungal drugs of General action-Pimafutsin, Irunin, clotrimazole, Nystatin, Flucanazole and others;

Locally acting preparations-Levorinov mazi, Miconzol gel, Nisitatin maz;

Rinsing the mouth with 1% drinking soda after each meal

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